

PRIVATE DEVELOPMENT AND MODERN TRADITIONS OF RUSSIAN PUNCTUATION

To'rayeva Dilbar Meyliyevna

Qarshi State University senior lecturer

G-mail: dilbarturayeva270@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7762147>

Annotation: in this article, we will consider some aspects related to the latest development of modern Russian punctuation.

Kalit so'zlar: modern Russian punctuation, punctuation marks, manuscript, minimalism, normalised punctuation.

N.S.Valgina, in his book "Current problems of Russian punctuation", summed up his reasoning with such sentences: "today punctuation marks are not just a conditional sign of "taking" or a means of separating text parts to facilitate reading, but signs capable of deep understanding of the content of the text, redistributing the structural links of words in a sentence, and even a whole sentence,

Let's consider some aspects related to the recent development of modern Russian punctuation.

Activation of the use of emoticons in written communication. The increase in Virtual forms of communication marked a new stage in the development of punctuation. Recent research has shown that in the modern punctuation system, many characters, even words, are freeing up their place in emoticons (emoticons). The use of icons in online forms of communication is 10-20 percent (the main user is young people, most are girls). The main reason why emoticons are becoming more and more popular is that they are not only strict and reliable, but also mujmal and ambiguous. David Crystal argues that emoticons do not completely fall out of use, because they are a necessary tool for expressing semantic paint and emotions in the speech of the layer – young people active in virtual communication".

The fact that in artistic creativity it becomes a habit to completely abandon punctuation marks. N.S.While Valgina focuses on this situation, "it's very difficult to look at it positively, especially a.R.About Chekhov's analogy of punctuation marks to the notes of understanding the text, K.G.Considering paustovsky's opinion that" punctuation keeps the text, does not allow it to decompose." Both of them are famous stylists and connoisseurs of the Russian language, authors of large-scale and immortal works. Especially if in written text it is firmly established that punctuation marks are important both structurally, semantically and intonationally", he says. He continues his argument by arguing that in fiction, authors are sometimes becoming accustomed to break the norms of literary language for a specific purpose, without any purpose, or vice versa. Of course, this condition occurs only in fiction. N.S.Valgina believes that there can only be two reasons for this: the first is that creators, whose main focus is on internal emotions, mental influence, do not think about punctuation marks, do not pay attention (therefore, punctuation marks are not found in their manuscripts either); the second is an attempt by authors to create a distinctive feature, an artistic priome, an individual style.

N.S.Valgina A.Pushkin claims that he is serious about the role of punctuation marks, there are clear grounds for this. His «Я помню чудное мгновенье» quoting an excerpt from a manuscript variant of the poem that uses no punctuation, “apparently, a. For Pushkin, it was not so important how these lines were printed. The characters here do not need the reader, including the modern reader: the lines are so musical, The sounds so awake that they are told that everything is enough on its own, there is no need for additional tools to understand the meaning:

*Я помню чудное мгновенье
Передо мной явилась ты
Как мимолетное виденье
Как гений чистой красоты*

And under it brings a printed variant of this poem with punctuation marks:

*Я помню чудное мгновенье:
Передо мной явилась ты,
Как мимолетное виденье,
Как гений чистой красоты.*

This tradition, in turn, also entered Uzbek literature. B.Bahriddinova says of this: even the complete abandonment of punctuation marks influenced by world literature in the style of writers of the later period can be seen as a special methodological application.

A number of problems have arisen with the punctuation of social networks. David Crystal points out that social network punctuation should be studied in two directions: the first, minimalism – the application of all punctuation marks by placing them tightly together; the second direction, maximization-the use of a certain punctuation mark in a row, several times in a row. For example, in social networks, the activity of the question mark increased. Even the fact that communicants rarely use it alone, mainly in complex use «????????????????????» is being watched. The number of exclamation marks used in the desire to express a person's emotion, admiration in writing, the importance of the question being asked, the desire to get an answer to it faster were indicated by the number of interrogative marks. For example, «У меня есть отличная новость!» «Она как-нибудь связана с новым годом?» «Да, и тебя она касается лично». «Рассказывай!» (спустя время) «Что случилось???????????????? Как это касается меня????? ??????» or: «Выходи!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!! Я тебя уже жду!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!»

This situation also began to be reflected in the Uzbek artistic style. For Example, “X. Do’stmuhammad The use of a series of punctuation marks in a unique way in the style of also determines the individuality of the author: – Qayerdasaannn?????!!!! – deya oh chekadi. Tap topmay takrorlayveradi: – Qayerdasaannn?????!!!! (“Men – sensiz, Sen – mensiz”)

In Russian, as in English and Uzbek, many questions have arisen related to the use of a series of punctuation marks in complex construction constuctions. For example,

Whether a point is placed at the end of a sentence in the following case?: *Я читаю роман “Кто виноват?”*. In the following case, the extract does not indicate whether the sentence-closing quotation applies?: *Профессор указывает, что “в золотой фонд литературы вошли такие произведения русской классики, как “Евгений Онегин”*”.

Does the sentence use the same quotation marks or two different ones if an interrogative or exclamation mark is used between the inner and outer quotation marks?:

Which punctuation mark is saved in the following cases?: *Не только песен нет, куда девался сон; всё подозрительно, и всё его тревожит. / Появились в продаже дачная*

мебель: столы, стулья, диваны и т.д./ У него было три дочери: Вера, Надежда, Любовь.; Вся эта область – дно моря в прошлом.

It should also be noted that no matter how progressive the approaches to the study of punctuation marks are, even at the new stage of the development of Russian punctuation marks, traditional views remain the leader. The reason is that while traditional normative punctuation makes it easier to understand a text, non – normative-non-regulatory punctuation prevents everyone from correctly understanding and understanding the content of the same text. Therefore, the normalized punctuation of the language in all periods is considered within the framework of the problem of the linguistic Department. To date, even in the Russian punctuation system, three main directions – syntactic, logical, intonation-remain dominant in determining the principles of application of punctuation. In the late XX century, among these dated traditional directions, attention began to be paid to the aspect of clarifying the important necessary fragments for information – the communicative purpose – through punctuation marks in communicative-written speech. The issue of separation of the communicative task was related to the traditional main task of punctuation marks - a system of non-letter characters in the alphabet that served to correctly express oral speech in writing, which also made it clear to the reader for what purpose the writer applied.

References:

1. Punktatsiya. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>
2. Baxriddinova B.M. Zamonaviy o'zbek punktatsiyasi asoslari. Monografiya. –Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2015. – 64 b.
3. Shoabdurahmonov Sh. O'zbek tilida punktatsiya. – Toshkent: 1955.
4. Nazarov K. O'zbek tili punktatsiyasi. - Toshkent: "O'qituvchi", 1976.
5. Zamonaviy o'zbek punktatsiyasining dolzarb muammolari. "Ma'rifat", 2014 y., № 94
6. O'zbek tilining punktatsiya qoidalari "Til va adabiyot ta'limi" Toshkent, 2015 yil, 1- 7-sonlar
7. Крысин Л.П. К соотношению системы языка, его нормы и узуса // Коммуникативные исследования: Научный журнал. – 2017. – № 2 (12). – С. 20-31.
8. Biyanova M.V. Punktatsionnye sistemy: sinxronnyy i diaxronnyy aspekty: avtoref. diss. ... kand. filol.nauk. – Ijevsk, 2010. – 24 s. – S 3.
9. Kobrina N.A., Malaxovskiy L.V. Angliyskaya punktatsiya: Uchebnoe posobie. – Moskva: Izdatel'stvo literatury na inostrannykh yazykakh, 1959. –110 s. – S.10